

Activity Report 2025

By the EDCH Coordination Team

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Introduction

This report presents the activities of the European Diamond Capacity Hub (EDCH) during its first year of operation in 2025. Following its official launch in Madrid, the first year of the EDCH focused on establishing an effective governance, launching an operational service catalogue, and supporting a powerful network of National Capacity Centres (NCCs) for Diamond Open Access (OA).

The EDCH in figures

6 services offered and hosted by 7 partner organisations
5 Task Forces led by 10 partner organisations
7 person coordination team
3 governing bodies
5 supporting members and funders for the EDCH
20 National Capacity Centres
205 organisations listed in the Registry
30 EDCH presentations, in person or online
An average annual budget of €600,000

EDCH key figures for 2025.

Definition and mission of the European Diamond Capacity Hub (EDCH)

The EDCH is a programme hosted by the OPERAS research infrastructure, officially launched in January 2025 in Madrid.

The objective of the EDCH is to facilitate, at the European level, the establishment of a harmonised, high-quality and sustainable scholarly communication infrastructure, managed and controlled by the scientific community.

Its main purpose is to promote the quality of Diamond OA publications in Europe, and to increase their visibility and recognition. In this context, the EDCH aims to ensure improvements in quality and capacity, as well as the harmonisation of Diamond OA publication services and outputs provided by publishers, service providers and infrastructures in Europe.

The EDCH leads the following tasks:

- Coordinate and streamline services and practices between National Capacity Centres (NCCs) and Institutional Capacity Centres (ICCs) in Europe (alternatively, in the ERA); implement and monitor the Diamond Open Access Standard (DOAS).¹
- Create synergies, strengthen complementarity and promote subsidiarity between existing European NCCs, and to stimulate the creation of new NCCs across Europe.
- Manage a portal for shared resources such as those produced by the DIAMAS and CRAFT-OA projects.
- Pool and redistribute resources and services for Diamond OA in Europe as needed at local, national or regional level.
- Facilitate and support the transition of scientific journals in Europe to Diamond OA.
- Represent Europe in the global framework for Diamond OA coordinated by UNESCO.

¹ Consortium of the DIAMAS Project. (2025). Diamond Open Access Standard (DOAS). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15128179>

Supporting members & Funders

Supporting members

The **French National Research Agency (ANR)** is the funding agency for project-based research in France. As a public institution under the authority of the French Ministry of Higher Education and Research, the ANR funds and promotes basic and applied research in all disciplines at the national, European, and international level. It also funds technological innovation, technology transfer, and

partnerships between research teams from the public and private sectors, in addition to strengthening dialogue between science and society.

The ANR also serves as the main operator of the France 2030 Investment Plan in higher education and research. France 2030 supports excellence and transformations in higher education, research, training, and innovation within priority sectors.

The ANR is strongly committed to supporting Open Science, built around three main objectives its Open Science policy is fully in line with the French National Plans for Open Science: Developing a concerted approach on the national, European and international level - Contributing to the sharing and opening of Research data, source code and software - Promoting full and immediate Open Access to scientific publications.

Funding allocated: 250,000 EUR over 18 months.

The **National Centre for Scientific Research (CNRS)** is the largest French public organization dedicated to scientific research. Covering various scientific fields, including the humanities and social sciences,

CNRS ranks as the third-largest research centre globally. Its primary mission is to identify, conduct, or support research that contributes to scientific, technological, social, and cultural progress in the country.

Since its inception, CNRS has embraced a multidisciplinary approach and promotes dialogue among different scientific disciplines as well as with societal stakeholders. It regularly participates in numerous European projects aimed at promoting open scholarly communication in the field of social sciences and humanities. It is also responsible for the OpenEdition infrastructure, which plays a pivotal role in the establishment of OPERAS and the development of open science on a European scale.

Funding allocated: 85,000 EUR over 24 months.

Gates Foundation

As the world's largest private philanthropic organisation, the **Gates Foundation** is committed to tackling some of the most pressing challenges of our time. Since its creation in 2000, the Foundation has been driven by the belief that every life has equal value and that progress is possible when science, innovation, and collaboration come together. Headquartered in Seattle and working in more than 140 countries, the Gates Foundation focuses on reducing health inequities, fighting infectious diseases, supporting agricultural development, advancing gender equality, and improving access to quality education. With over \$83 billion in grants awarded since its inception, it plays a unique role in mobilizing knowledge, resources, and partnerships at a global scale. In September 2025, the Gates Foundation extended its support to the European Diamond Capacity Hub (EDCH) through a [three-year grant](#). This contribution strengthens the EDCH's mission to build a sustainable and high-quality infrastructure for Diamond Open Access publishing in Europe, fostering equity, collaboration, and innovation in scholarly communication.

Funding allocated: \$500,000 over 3 years

Funders

**Funded by
the European Union**

The **European Commission** is the executive branch of the European Union, responsible for proposing legislation, implementing decisions, and managing the day-to-day affairs of the EU. One of its key roles is to support research, innovation, and development through various funding programs and initiatives.

Through calls for projects, the European Commission provides financial assistance to a wide range of initiatives that align with its strategic priorities, such as sustainable development, technological advancement, and social inclusion. This funding aims to foster collaboration among researchers, businesses, and organisations across Europe, facilitating the exchange of knowledge and expertise.

By investing in projects that address pressing societal challenges, the European Commission plays a crucial role in driving progress and ensuring that Europe remains at the forefront of global innovation. As part of its commitment to Open Science, the Commission actively supports **Diamond Open Access**, a model in which scholarly publications are free for both authors and readers, without article processing charges (APCs). Through programs like **Horizon Europe**, it funds initiatives that strengthen community-driven publishing infrastructures, ensuring equitable and sustainable access to knowledge for all.

EU contribution for the [Diamas project](#): 2,518,057.50 EUR from September 2022 to August 2025.

EU contribution for the [CRAFT-OA project](#): 4,777,337.50 EUR from January 2023 to December 2025.

The Foundation for Science and Technology (FCT) is the Portuguese national public agency that supports research in science, technology, and innovation in all areas of knowledge. It is a special public institute under the supervision and oversight of the Ministry of Education, Science, and Innovation. The mission of FCT is to continuously promote the advancement of scientific and technological knowledge in Portugal, achieve the highest international standards of quality and competitiveness in all scientific and technological fields, and stimulate its dissemination and contribution to society and the economic and societal development.

In October 2025, the EDCH received a grant from FCT. FCT financially supports the EDCH in the context of the Portuguese national Diamond OA initiative PublIn that is managed by the FCCN, FCT's digital services and Minho University. This support will strengthen the EDCH's activities, including outreach, training, and engagement with local stakeholders. It demonstrates the strong connection between European-level coordination and national initiatives, which helps ensure that Diamond Open Access publishing is sustainable, high-quality, and widely accessible.

The EDCH received a donation of 12,000 EUR for 2025.

Governance

Prior to and following its official launch, the EDCH established and launched its governance and operational structures.

Several structures have been established to ensure operational efficiency:

- **The Steering Committee:**

The Steering Committee is composed of public and not for profit organisations (e.g. charities, foundations, associations, RFOs, RPOs) that financially contribute to the EDCH. It brings together the EDCH's supporting members and funders, currently comprises representatives from the ANR, the CNRS and the Gates Foundation, chaired by Lidia Borrel-Damián (Science Europe), and meets quarterly. Four meetings of the Steering Committee were held in 2025.

- **The Executive Committee:**

The Executive Committee oversees the EDCH's daily operations. National and international organisations involved in various aspects of Diamond OA publishing – are part of this committee and contribute in kind by leading key EDCH Task Forces and Services. It brings together the EDCH coordination team with the task leads of the five task forces that implement the strategic directions adopted by the Steering Committee and meets on a monthly basis.

- **The Coordination Team:**

The EDCH Coordination Team is the backbone of the organisation, ensuring seamless coordination, management, communication and administration of the EDCH. It supports and coordinates the Assembly, the Steering and Executive Committees, and the Task Forces to guarantee the efficient implementation of EDCH's joint programmes and projects. Currently, it comprises seven roles: co-coordinators, executive manager, communications and outreach officer, community manager, policy officer, OA books manager and federated infrastructure manager and meets on a weekly basis.

- **The 5 Task Forces:**

The operation and sustainability of the European Diamond Capacity Hub are supported by the collective efforts of five specialised Task Forces, each addressing critical aspects of functionality and long-term impact. They bring together partner organisations that are committed to contributing at an operational level to the EDCH and its catalogue of services. The following themes each have their own Task Force: community, funding, quality alignment, skills and competences, and tools and technology.

All of these governance and management bodies operate in accordance with the procedures and regulations set out in a series of documents drawn up and adopted during the EDCH's first year of operation: the Terms of Reference² for the EDCH and for each Task Force.

² https://edch.eu/sites/default/files/EDCH_ToR_approved_March_2026.pdf (finalised in March 2026)

Communication and community engagement

Throughout 2025, the EDCH invested significantly in communication and community engagement to raise awareness among the various communities who are likely to be interested in the EDCH, its resources and its services, in the European Research Area. Related activities have focused on four areas:

The establishment and development of communication tools:

- Launch of [the EDCH website](#)
The main website of the EDCH (domain name edch.eu) which serves as the central entry point for the initiative. The site outlines the scope, activities and governance of the EDCH, and provides access to all the services and resources.
- Creation and development of the EDCH's social media accounts
Set up dedicated accounts to ensure the infrastructure's visibility and the dissemination of its activities to the Diamond OA community:
 - A LinkedIn account³
 - A Bluesky account⁴
 - A presence on YouTube via a dedicated channel hosted on the OPERAS account⁵
- Development of the visual identity
Creation of a comprehensive visual identity for the EDCH, including colour schemes, typography and logos. In addition, a presentation brochure and a step-by-step guide have been produced to facilitate the communities' understanding and adoption of the services⁶
- Launch of the EDCH Advocates network
Establishment of a network of Diamond OA experts who function as advocates on behalf of the EDCH to promote its activities and services within the Diamond OA community.

Engagement with communities through presentations at relevant events

- Presence at community events
In 2025, 30 EDCH presentations were delivered by the coordination team, EDCH Advocates, and EDCH partners. These presentations took place at various conferences (PUBMET 2025, EASE Conference, OASPA Annual Conference), webinars (organised by UNESCO), as well as internal meetings to which the EDCH was invited (Couperin and the CoSO Publications Committee).
- EDCH event organisation

³ <https://www.linkedin.com/company/eudch/>

⁴ <https://bsky.app/profile/eudch.bsky.social>

⁵ <https://www.youtube.com/playlist?list=PLNSNT11cPt5YFIqG7EyTzsj0Q-t-Ldvqk>

⁶ <https://edch.eu/communication-kit>

The EDCH also organised five webinars dedicated to presenting its services, in English, French and Spanish, in order to strengthen community engagement and encourage the adoption of its resources. The webinars were attended by a total of approximately 350 participants.

The Forum: facilitating our communities via the discussion spaces we provide.

- Launch and management of the EDCH Forum
As the main channel for exchange and engagement, the Forum facilitates discussion, knowledge sharing and the dissemination of key information relating to the activities of the Diamond OA community.
 - Forum usage indicators:
 - 264 registered members in 2025
 - 42,033 page views in 2025⁷;

Total numbers of pageviews (2025)

- DAU/MAU ratio : 14.5% on average for 2025;

⁷ This number includes logged-in users and anonymous users and excludes any automated traffic (i.e. search engine crawlers and bots).

Total % of DAU/MAU per month (2025)

- 176 discussion topics created and 442 replies in 2025 (April 2025–December 2025)

Numbers of topics and posts created (2025)

- The establishment of a network of National Capacity Centres (NCCs) to amplify our communication efforts. The network of National Capacity Centres is currently being established and is growing rapidly.

NCCs are national or regional support structures that bring together Diamond OA

publishers, service providers, and infrastructures to support high-quality scholarly publications. NCCs are strategically important because they understand local academic traditions, higher education structures, national policies, and publication in national languages. NCCs will eventually provide the following services:

- Shared technical infrastructure and tools
- Training and policy guidance for institutions and national funders
- Advocacy for sustainable publishing models
- Alignment with the services of the EDCH, and assessment of Diamond OA journals: Diamond OA Standard, Diamond Discovery Hub
- Feedback to the EDCH the needs and priorities of the national Diamond OA communities, and add elements to the EDCH services (e.g. Training).

The network's first meeting, held in June 2025, brought together 15 NCCs. To date, the network comprises 20 NCCs, including:

- 11 established centres;
- 9 centres that are currently being set up.

Finally, all organisations involved in the Diamond publishing landscape are invited to register with the EDCH Registry. The Registry closed 2025 with 205 registered organisations. A map is available to help locate these organisations:

<https://registry.edch.eu/organisations-map>

Service catalogue

In parallel, the EDCH operational members have been working on structuring the service catalogue. Today, a portfolio of operational services are offered free of charge to the community. The EDCH's main website, <https://edch.eu>, presents the EDCH and serves as the landing page for its services, thereby providing a single point of access to the entire EDCH ecosystem. This is a Drupal content management system hosted by the "Poznan Supercomputer and Networking Center" (PCSS), and maintained by the EDCH coordination team.

- **The EDCH Registry**, <https://registry.edch.eu>, a platform for registering, cataloguing and discovering organisations that are part of the Diamond OA community. Organisations can thus showcase their services and expertise and establish new collaborations:.. This Drupal instance is also hosted by PCSS and maintained by the EDCH coordination team.
- **The EDCH Forum**, <https://forum.edch.eu>, provides a discussion space for all members of the European Diamond OA community and organisations registered in the Registry. This service is hosted directly by Discourse and is run and moderated by the EDCH coordination team with the support of various community members.
- The **Diamond Discovery Hub (DDH)**, <https://ddh.edch.eu/>, a list of Diamond OA journals, developed from scratch and maintained through a collaboration between DOAJ, ICM Warsaw University and the University of Göttingen.
- The **Diamond Open Access Standard (DOAS)**, <https://selfassessment.edch.eu/>, which aims to harmonise the quality and best practices of Diamond stakeholders, and its self-assessment tool ("EDCH Self-assessment tool"), enabling publishers and service providers to verify their compliance with the seven components of the DOAS standard as well as their financial viability. This service was developed and is maintained by FECYT. The self-assessment tool already has 1,647 registered users. 214 self-assessments have already been completed by Diamond publishing services, and 327 self-assessments are currently in progress.
- **The EDCH Training Platform** ("EDCH Training"), <https://training.edch.eu>, offering training on the seven components of the DOAS standard. This service, based on the Moodle platform, is hosted and maintained by OpenEdition.
- **The EDCH Resources and Guidelines**, <https://resources.edch.eu>, a web portal bringing together a collection of complementary resources aligned with the recommendations of the DOAS standard, to support the transition to Diamond OA. This is another Drupal instance, hosted by EIFL, with content maintained jointly by EIFL and the EDCH coordination team.
- **Publishing tools**, <https://edch.eu/publishing-tools>, a guide to scientific indexing

services and a set of OJS components for publishers and publishing platform: The guide and components are provided by various teams including OpenEdition, TIB and Masaryk University Press.

A technical monitoring mechanism, <https://status.edch.eu/>, is also available and provides an overview of the availability of EDCH services. This monitoring page, provided by a professional service provider, is managed by the EDCH coordination team to ensure the smooth operations of the EDCH main website and services.

As the EDCH is a federated infrastructure, the various services included in the catalogue have been developed as part of collaborative projects funded by the European Commission. This distributed structure has the advantage of spreading the development and maintenance workload across a network of partner organisations. However, it requires significant harmonisation work at technical, legal and organisational levels. The following mechanisms have been put in place for this purpose:

Technical services:

- Technical choices and developments are discussed within various working groups, such as the EDCH Tools and Technology Task Force (EDCH TTTF). The TTTF is a forum for discussion involving representatives from all parties actively involved in providing EDCH services, as well as members of the wider community. This enables a shared vision, the sharing of experience, and thus takes into account the needs, feedback and recommendations of the EDCH community. Other discussion channels are available for exchanges requiring more targeted communication, for example, for internal discussions amongst EDCH service providers.
- Technical coordination is discussed weekly at EDCH coordination team meetings, in order to jointly define priorities and report on the progress of various tasks.
- A service availability monitoring platform to track and monitor the status of the various services in real time. This platform also allows users to subscribe to track ongoing work or incidents.
- A centralised collection of usage data, enabling the monitoring of trends in the use of various services, using a Matomo-based service provided by OPERAS. This service enables uptake and engagement with the EDCH and its services.
- A GitHub organisation⁸ has been created to host various EDCH software components, ensuring the long-term viability and maintenance of these components.
- A transition of the EDCH services to a common domain name, which is no longer

⁸ <https://github.com/eudch>

linked to a European project, has taken place. Services initially accessible via subdomains of diamas.org are now accessible via edch.eu domains⁹.

- To ensure the long-term viability of various services after the end of their funding under a European project, the hosting arrangements for certain services have been reviewed, and the Drupal services initially operated by a subcontractor of a European project are now hosted by institutions that are active in-kind partners of the EDCH and OPERAS.
- Another important aspect is the groundwork being laid for the implementation of a federated authentication and authorisation platform (“Federated AAI”), enabling users to access EDCH services using their existing identity—such as an institutional identity—rather than having to create a new identity for each EDCH service. This work is currently underway.
- Substantive tasks with longer-term objectives are also underway, covering, for example, the harmonisation of interfaces, tools and practices, as well as a common approach to digital accessibility.

⁹ The transition from the diamas.org domain to edch.eu started in 2025 and was finalised in March 2026.

Legal and organisational framework

Various priority areas for harmonisation have been identified and developed within the framework of the various projects supporting EDCH's activities:

- The establishment of Memoranda of Understanding (MoUs) and Operational Level Agreements (OLAs) between service providers and the EDCH formalises the roles and responsibilities of the parties involved in the organisation of the EDCH's services. This work on the agreements forms part of a more systemic approach to IT service management, drawing on a formal framework such as FitSM¹⁰ and integrating with the OPERAS service management system. A corollary of implementing these agreements is the alignment of technical practices; the OLAs include common requirements and provide a technical framework for service delivery by addressing various aspects such as the GDPR, recommended best practices, or common requirements regarding IT security. These activities aim to ensure that the information provided to users is harmonised and appropriate. This is both particularly important in the context of European regulations such as the GDPR, and particularly complicated for a distributed infrastructure such as that of the EDCH.
- From an organisational perspective, the EDCH Terms of Reference were discussed and adopted by the Steering Committee. These Terms define the various levels of governance within the EDCH and the formal relationship with OPERAS. The following organisational chart provides a brief overview of this structure. The respective roles of the Coordination Team members have also been clearly defined in an annexed document.

¹⁰ <https://www.fitsm.eu/>

EDCH Governance

Business model

The EDCH's activities were able to commence in 2025 thanks to grants from [several funding bodies](#), including the ANR, the CNRS, the Gates Foundation and the FCCN/FCT. Another significant source of funding for the EDCH is the European Commission's calls for proposals: the EU-funded DIAMAS and CRAFT-OA projects laid the groundwork for the EDCH. While time-limited project funding provides valuable support, there is a need for more stable funding mechanisms that would enable permanent structures such as the EDCH to plan strategically for the long term and ensure the sustainability of its services. The EDCH intends to establish membership fee mechanisms for various stakeholders – ministries, research agencies, National Capacity Centres (NCCs) and Institutional Capacity Centres (ICCs) – to complement one-time project funding. This is why, from its inception, the EDCH team has been engaged in a process of reflection to establish a sustainable economic model. This work has been undertaken in collaboration with the Funding Task Force and other stakeholders, such as the OPERAS coordination team. An initial business case has been produced and will be used to develop an economic model during the second half of 2026. At the same time, a budget and work plan for 2025 and 2026 have been prepared and

implemented, incorporating both the EDCH's financial income and in-kind contributions from its partners.

Partnerships

During the same period, the EDCH developed a policy of active partnerships in Europe and beyond.

A significant part of this partnership activity involved preparing new projects in response to calls for proposals from the European Commission. The EDCH has successfully responded to the HORIZON-WIDERA-2025-06-ERA-02 call, which will enable us to launch the AEGIS-OA project in March 2026, in partnership with 23 other organisations across Europe.

At the same time, it has established a partnership with CERN under the framework agreement between the European Commission and 13 research and research funding organisations, for the deployment of the new version of the ORE platform. The EDCH, represented by OPERAS in this partnership, has been entrusted with two tasks: (1) to co-ordinate the Task Force dedicated to Communication for the new platform; and (2) to engage the Diamond community—both journals and platforms—to work in partnership with ORE.

Finally, the EDCH works closely with the Diamond Action Plan Steering Committee to participate in the global dialogue on Diamond OA. The EDCH have actively participated in the preparation and organisation of the global summits on Diamond Open Access in South Africa and India, in collaboration with UNESCO, and in the regular webinars of the Diamond Action Plan Community.

In summary

2025 was the year in which the infrastructure for the EDCH was rolled out, in technical, legal, organisational, financial and communication terms. The year 2026 will enable us to make the most of this infrastructure so that as many stakeholders as possible at European level can take ownership of it and use it to advance the Diamond OA publishing model across the continent.